

COMPARATIVE AND FUNCTIONAL STUDY OF PHONOLOGICAL UNITS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

Obidov Qahramonjon Xoshimjonovich

2nd year student of master's degree

English linguistics major

Fergana state university

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7895338>

Annotation: It is important to study phonological units in linguistics. In this article, various aspects of phonological units in English and Uzbek languages are studied and discussed.

Keywords: typology, science, comparative, linguistic, gender, learning, potential, method.

INTRODUCTION

The word typology consists of two Greek morphemes: a) typos means type and b) logos means science or word. Typology is a branch of science which is typical to all sciences without any exception. In this respect their typological method is not limited with the sphere of one science. It has a universal rise. So typology may be divided into:

- Non-linguistic and
- Linguistic typology

Non-linguistic typology is the subject matter of the sciences except linguistics.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Linguistic typology is a new branch of general linguistics which studies the systems of languages comparatively, also finds common laws of languages and establishes differences and similarities between them.

According to the notion of comparison of linguistics phenomenon and the aim directed on we may classify linguistic typology into the following parts a) genetic or genealogical typology, b) structural typology, c) areal typology and d) comparative typology.

Genealogical typology is a branch of linguistic typology which studies the similarities and the relationship between the related languages. It is applied to the systems of genetically related languages. Genealogical typology developed from the comparative - historical linguistics dominated during the 19th century in Europe. Its origin was stimulated by the discovery of Sanskrit, the ancient classical language of India. The discovery of Sanskrit disclosed the possibility of a comparative study of languages.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Before the discovery of Sanskrit European linguistics possessed very vague similarities for the current grammars built on the Greek model. They didn't set clearly the features of each languages. It is worth to mention that at the same time Sanskrit discovery gave rise to confuse notions of linguistic relation which lived for a brief time that European languages were derived from Sanskrit. But this opinion gave way to a correct explanation, namely Sanskrit, Latin, Greek, and other were later forms of one prehistorically language.

Comparatives gave two kinds of classification of languages - genealogical and morphological.

Genealogical classification deals with the family relationship of languages which descend from one common ancestor. It distributes languages into different families.

Structural typology research makes it possible to establish some traits are *universal, unique, and special*.

The notion of language universals is closely connected with the process of unification of linguistic facts with a process of establishing common features between the systems of different languages.

In the linguistic literature phoneme is defined as the smallest distinctive unit. Unlike the other bigger units of language as morpheme and word it doesn't have its meaning but helps us to distinct the meanings of words and morphemes. Comp. boy-toy, better-letter-latter-litter-later; bola-tola-xola-ola, non-qon-son- on, un-un(tovush)-o'n-o'ng(mos), bo'z(o'zlashtirilmagan) – bo'z(material) etc. From the acoustic and articulatory points of view the phonemic system of any language may be divided into vowels and consonants.

From the acoustic point of the view vowels are speech sounds of pure musical tone. Their oscillographic melody tracing are characterized by periodically.

From the point of view of articulation vowels are speech sound in the production of which there are no noise producing obstructions. The obstructions by means of which vowels are formed may be of two kinds:

- The fourth obstruction without which neither vowels nor voiced consonants are formed.
- The third obstruction characteristic of both: English and Uzbek vowels. The channels formed in the mouth cavity for vowel production by moving a certain part of the tongue and keeping the lips in a certain position cannot be regarded as obstructions. They change the shape and volume of the resonance chamber, and in this way, help to achieve the timbre (or quality) of voice, characteristic of the vowel in question.

The first comparative vowel tables appeared in the 19th-century. Their aim was to prove the common origin of some two modern languages belonging to the same family. In the 1920s of the XX century Prof. D. Jones suggested a classification based on the principle of the so called «cardinal vowels». But these cardinal vowels are abstract notion and have nothing to do with the comparison of two language from the typological viewpoint.

The aim of our comparison is pedagogical. Every phoneme of the English language should be compared with the' Uzbek vowels as comparison of an unknown language phoneme with that of one's mother tongue is of great use. The aim of our comparison (does not need any universal principle) and is to underline the specific features of vowel formation in the two languages in question.

CONCLUSION

The main philological relevant features of the Uzbek vowels phonemes are: front-central-back, according to which they may form phonological opposition: close-mid-open (sil-sel-sal - kir-ko'r, qo'l - kel, tor - ter etc.)

The idea of my work is showed the novelty of the work, which contains the comparative analyses of the English language with the Uzbek language.

Example: "I am sitting" in Uzbek language to express this tense is used only simple tense "Men o'tiraman".

References:

1. Egamberdiyeva D.U. The essence of the method of video-English. Conference materials. 2016.
2. Kadyrovna, A. D. (2022). METHODOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF TEACHING THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE. Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal, 3(10), 1295-1298.
3. Kadirovna, A. D., & Mahmudovna, A. D. (2022). CULTURE OF SPEECH OF THE TEACHER WHEN LEARNING RUSSIAN. Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal, 3(11), 891-894.
4. Адилова, Д., & Раджапова, Н. (2021). Развитие многоязычия в Узбекистане, выбор второго иностранного языка. Общество и инновации, 2(5/S), 100-103.
5. Shadmanova, N. I., & Adilova, D. K. (2020). SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL ANALYSIS OF THE CONCEPT OF CIVILIZATION. Theoretical & Applied Science, (4), 168-171.
6. Madatovna, K. M. (2022, December). TEACHING LISTENING IN ENGLISH LESSONS IN HIGHER EDUCATION. In INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE (Vol. 1, No. 9, pp. 53-57).

7. Madatovna, K. M. (2022). APPROACHES AND METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH: ORAL APPROACH, SITUATIONAL LANGUAGE TEACHING AND AUDIO-SPEECH METHOD. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(11), 91-94.
8. Jabborov, N. (2021). The history of the text and some comments on its genesis. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(6), 632-636.
9. Abdulkhakimovich, J. N., & Khazratovna, X. S. (2019). THE MANUSCRIPTS OF THE NOVEL "ZUBDATU-T-TAVORIKH" BY AGAKHI AND ITS VALUE AS A SOURCE OF LITERATURE. *Journal of Critical Reviews*, 7(6), 2020.
10. Хайдарова, О. К. (2021). НАУКА И МИР. НАУКА И МИР Учредители: Издательство Научное обозрение, 2(4), 52-54.
11. Хайдарова, О. К., & Бокиев, Б. У. (2016). Педагогический опыт преподавателя на современном этапе. *Молодой ученый*, (11), 1572-1574.
12. Гаппарова, Т. Г., & Хайдарова, О. К. (2013). ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОЕ ОБЩЕНИЕ КАК ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОЕ ЗВЕНО В ТВОРЧЕСТВЕ УЧИТЕЛЯ. *SCIENCE AND WORLD*, 47.
13. Akbarova, L. U. (2023). MAMLAKATLARNING IQTISODIY INTEGRATSIYA JARAYONLARIDAGI ISHTIROKINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA RAQAMLI MARKETING TECHNOLOGIYALARIDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH USULLARI. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 3(1-2), 84-91.
14. Tojimatov, I., Usmonova, S., Muhammadmusayeva, M., & Xoldarova, S. (2023). DATA MINING MASALALARI VA ULARNING YECHIMLARI. "TRENDS OF MODERN SCIENCE AND PRACTICE", 1(2), 60-63.
15. Kimyonazarova, D., Ne'matjonova, D., Ergasheva, B., & Tojimatov, I. (2023, March). KATTA MA'LUMOTLAR BILAN ISHLASHDA HADOOP ARXITEKTURASI. In *Международная конференция академических наук (Vol. 2, No. 3, pp. 96-99)*.
16. Muratova, G. R., & Komilova, M. (2022). PARALIMPIYA SPORTI IMKONIYATLARI CHEKLANGAN SHAHSLARNI IJTIMOIYLASHTIRISH USULI SIFATIDA. *Oriental Art and Culture*, 3(2), 697-701.
17. Muratova, G. R. (2021). To the problems of self-assessment of children with disabilities through adaptive physical education and sport. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(10), 455-458.
18. Муратова, Г. Р. (2020). ВОПРОСЫ СТРАТЕГИЧЕСКОГО УПРАВЛЕНИЯ В СФЕРЕ ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ И СПОРТА В ФЕРГАНСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ. *ИННОВАЦИИ В ПЕДАГОГИКЕ И ПСИХОЛОГИИ*, (SI).

19. Asqarova, S. I. (2020). Terminology Of The Direction Of Language Contacts In Modern Linguistics. Scientific Bulletin Of Namangan State University, 2(11), 234-239.

